

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TELEVISION AND THE RULING AUTHORITIES IN THE WESTERN BALKANS

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Abstract: In the Western Balkan countries, the media’s role as a watchdog and a corrective to those in power is heavily suppressed. Dependencies between authorities and broadcasters are prevalent in both public and commercial television sectors. Outlets critical of the government remain rare exceptions and are frequently subject to threats. This article examines contemporary instances of pressure and harassment against television journalists and media owners in the Western Balkans from 2019 onwards. Furthermore, it addresses the critical phenomenon of “media capture” by the state – a strategy employed to secure “political tranquility” and ensure biased reporting.

Keywords: television, media freedom, Western Balkans, media capture

“A free press can, of course, be good or bad, but, most certainly,
without freedom, a press will never be anything but bad.”

Albert Camus

In the Western Balkan countries¹, the restriction of media freedom² by state leaders, political parties, and/or prominent businessmen is a long-standing issue. For years, international non-governmental organizations such as Reporters Without Borders and Transparency International, as well as the U.S. State Department, have raised alarms regarding this trend. Owners of television channels, including veteran journalists, maintain close ties with the ruling authorities, effectively transforming their networks into pro-government media outlets. The few remaining broadcasters critical of the government are targeted with anti-journalistic rhetoric, harassment, and defamation lawsuits.

The COVID-19 pandemic further exacerbated the sector's problems, complicating the work of journalists and presenting them with new challenges and constraints. According to the 2021 World Press Freedom Index by Reporters Without Borders, media freedom deteriorated in all six countries, with the sole exception of Bosnia and Herzegovina, which saw a marginal improvement. The state of the media landscape in the region is also analyzed in European Commission reports, as freedom of expression and media freedom are core criteria for membership in the European Union³. Even more intensified control and censorship, including self-censorship, are observed in the editorial policies of national and regional television stations

¹Referring to the Republic of Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, the Republic of Kosovo, the Republic of North Macedonia, the Republic of Serbia, and Montenegro.

²This article does not address the increase in harassment of journalists resulting from their work in covering the COVID-19 pandemic.

³All countries in the region have declared their desire to become EU members: Montenegro and the Republic of Serbia are candidate countries in accession negotiations; the Republic of Albania and the Republic of North Macedonia are candidate countries, with the start of negotiations expected in the near future; Bosnia and Herzegovina and Kosovo are potential candidates for membership.

across the six countries. The media's role as a corrective to those in power is heavily suppressed, with dependencies between television networks and authorities being prevalent in both public service and private commercial broadcasters in the region.

As is the case in EU member states, television networks and their content in the Western Balkans are subject to strict regulations; however, in practice, these do not guarantee the independence of broadcasters from external factors and influences. The high number of television channels in all six countries is also not an indicator of quality, credible, or ethical reporting of events and processes. A joint report by the Peace Institute and the South East European Network for Professionalization of Media (SEENPM) cites a public opinion poll conducted by the market research company Ipsos for the "Resilience" project. According to the results, "television dominates as the primary and most frequently used source of information across the entire region". This conclusion is significantly important and partially explains the pressure exerted by the authorities on television networks in the region.

Attempts to restrict media freedoms are not isolated to the territory of the Western Balkans. In July 2021, a public hearing⁴ was held in the European Parliament, organized by the Committee on Culture and Education (CULT). The theme was "The Future of Media and Media Pluralism in Europe". During the hearing, Lutz Kinkel of the European Centre for Press and Media Freedom (ECPMF) stated: "It is no secret that media freedom in member states and accession countries in Eastern and Central Europe is deteriorating. The main reason is the non-compliance with European values and regulations by state actors. They are also a source of conspiracy theories, undermining journalism and threatening individual reporters, especially women. I have the feeling that we live in two realities: the one on paper and the one in which we actually live" (The Parliament Magazine, 14.07.2021). Tom Gibson of the Committee to Protect Journalists added: "What we see in many EU member states is a hostile environment for journalists" (Ibidem). It is no coincidence that within the Union, discussions have begun regarding the adoption of a Media Freedom Act, which, in the words of the European Commissioner for the Internal Market, Thierry Breton, aims to "ensure the integrity and independence of the EU media market" (Euractiv, 30.11.2021).

The trend observed in Europe (including Bulgaria), and not only in the Western Balkans, is "state media capture", which is also the title of the report by Marius Dragomir, cited in a study by the Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism. "Collusion between the political class and media owners has reached unprecedented levels, leading to a phenomenon known as media capture. A situation where all or the majority of media outlets operate as part of a cartel between the government and business, which controls and manipulates the flow of information in order to protect their unlimited and exclusive access to public resources" (Reuters Institute, 2021:15). Consequently, a deterioration of media freedom is observed across the entire EU.

According to the responses from surveys and interviews with journalists from Central and Eastern Europe conducted by teams from the Reuters Institute (Reuters Institute, 2021:10), six methods for restricting freedom of speech have been identified:

- Anti-journalistic rhetoric from politicians and competing media;
- Online harassment, threats, and physical assault;
- State media capture and the use of state advertising⁵ as a means of ensuring "political tranquility";

⁴The European Parliament website explains that committees organize hearings with the participation of experts "when this is essential to its work on a particular topic". More at:

<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/committees/bg/cult/events/events-hearings>.

⁵This method benefits pro-government media, which receive substantial advertising funds paid by state or municipal authorities and enterprises, while those critical of the authorities are deprived of the opportunity for additional government funding. The withdrawal of state advertising also influences private advertisers, who either reduce their volume of ads on the respective television station or refuse to enter into contracts with it.

- Deterioration of the legal framework for the protection of journalists;
- Concerns regarding the ability of journalists to protect their sources of information;
- Lack of cooperation and solidarity.

The aforementioned approaches are also employed in the Western Balkan countries. What follows is an examination of contemporary examples – not intended to be exhaustive – concerning television channels critical of the authorities across the six nations since 2019.

Republic of Albania

For years, the Prime Minister of the Republic of Albania, Edi Rama, has attempted to secure “political tranquility” by using various methods to minimize media outlets critical of his Socialist Party. Even before the coronavirus pandemic, in August 2019, Balkan Insight⁶ reported the cancellation of two television programs on News 24 for the following season. The shows “The Unrepresented” (Të Paekspozuarit) and “Krasta Show” were known for their critical coverage of Edi Rama’s cabinet policies. Their removal from the air once again raised questions about the level of media freedom in Albania and sparked doubts about political interference, as claimed by the host of “The Unrepresented”, Ylli Rakipi. The owner of the station, Irfan Hysenbelliu, denied being influenced by external factors (such as Prime Minister Rama) in his decision to terminate the contracts with the two production teams.

The authorities’ attempts to belittle and discredit the journalistic profession are not limited to insults from the Albanian Prime Minister, who has referred to journalists as “trash cans”. In May 2020, one of Albania’s most-watched broadcasters, Ora News, was ordered to suspend operations indefinitely and was fined by state health authorities for allegedly failing to maintain physical distancing during filming. According to the health authorities, the reason was an excessive number of guests in the studio – three interlocutors participated in an Ora News program instead of the permitted two. The station was also fined 2 million Albanian Lek (approximately 16,000 Euros). In the summer of 2020, the Albanian government took control of Ora News and Channel One on the grounds that their owner was accused of drug trafficking.

Another television channel under fire is Top Channel. In March 2021, police surrounded the station's building, allegedly due to the state’s unilateral termination of a lease agreement. The decision was made without prior notice, despite the lease being valid until 2025. The station’s troubles did not end there. According to the International Press Institute, on April 7, 2021, police took a Top Channel cameraman into custody while he was covering a football match between Tirana and Skënderbeu Korçë. He was taken to a police station in Tirana, where he claimed he was detained and beaten by high-ranking officers. The police maintained that the operator was detained for refusing to identify himself and denied any use of violence. The television station dismissed these police claims as false.

Bosnia and Herzegovina

⁶“The leading English-language website of the Balkan Investigative Reporting Network” (BIRN). More at: <https://balkaninsight.com/about-birn>.

Bosnia and Herzegovina⁷ is currently in a political crisis (Crisis Group, 2021), which is being further exacerbated with the help of the media. Milorad Dodik, the member of the tripartite Presidency of Bosnia and Herzegovina from the Republika Srpska quota, known for his nationalist views, continues his attempts to weaken the country's central government. He insists that Republika Srpska should sever most ties with the central government. Dodik has repeatedly made threats to establish a separate Serbian army and declare the administrative unit's independence (or join neighboring Republic of Serbia). In response to these attempts to undermine the state's integrity, in early January 2022, the U.S. administration imposed sanctions⁸ on several officials and a television station for alleged corruption and attempts to destabilize Bosnia and Herzegovina. The sanctions targeted Serbian political leader Milorad Dodik (head of the ruling Alliance of Independent Social Democrats), his advisor and former president of the High Judicial and Prosecutorial Council Milan Tegeltija, and the affiliated Alternativna Televizija (ATV). Since 2019, ATV has had a new owner, Mile Radišić, a Bosnian Serb tycoon allegedly close to Dodik.

Journalistic work is further hindered regarding access to public information. In Bosnia and Herzegovina, the Law on Freedom of Access to Information guarantees access to most public registers, but the Law on the Protection of Classified Information obstructs journalists from obtaining data.

The European Commission's report states: "No progress was made in guaranteeing freedom of expression and the media, in protecting journalists from threats and violence (through subsequent judicial action), nor in ensuring the financial sustainability of the public broadcasting system" (European Commission, a, 2021: 1–2). The 2021 Freedom House report asserts that "journalists face political pressure, harassment, threats, and attacks during their work" (Freedom House, 2021). It adds that private media are linked to political parties, while public broadcasters in the two administrative units (the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina and Republika Srpska) "often operate as party platforms" (Ibidem).

Republic of Kosovo

In February 2022, Reporters Without Borders (RSF) condemned anti-journalistic rhetoric in Kosovo in an open letter. The document stated that "individuals linked to the ruling party⁹ and the President¹⁰ turned the public against journalists after two media outlets¹¹ made an error¹², followed by a public apology" (RSF, Open Letter). According to the NGO, politicians and officials, including spokespersons and media advisors to the cabinet and the

⁷Bosnia and Herzegovina consists of two administrative units inhabited by different ethnic groups – Republika Srpska (with a predominantly Serbian population) and the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (with a predominantly Bosniak and Croatian population). This complex state structure is the result of the Dayton Peace Agreement (1995), which ended the war in Bosnia and Herzegovina (1992 – 1995). The goal was to create a unitary multicultural state.

⁸A ban on travel to the US and a freeze on all their assets on American territory.

⁹Referring to the Vetëvendosje (Self-Determination) party – Author's note.

¹⁰Referring to President Vjosa Osmani – Author's note. Vjosa Osmani-Sadriu is the sixth President of the Republic of Kosovo and the second woman to hold the office (term: since 4 April 2021).

¹¹In fact, three media outlets: the online edition Gazeta Express, the online portal Ekonomia Online, and the public broadcaster Radio Television of Kosovo (RTK). Subsequently, all three publicly apologized.

¹²On February 4, the Kosovo online edition Gazeta Express published an article about MPs' travel expenses along with an editor's note to the author. The editor's suggestion concerned a sentence reporting President Vjosa Osmani's claim of saving taxpayers' money. The comment read: "It can be removed, unless you want to attack Vjosa". Before the outlet deleted the note, Ekonomia Online and RTK republished the unedited post on Facebook, making the case widely known.

Vetëvendosje (Self-Determination) party, posted comments on social networks that “serve to incite the public against journalists and reporters” (Ibidem). Speaking on behalf of the parties they represent, they implied that the media had attempted to undermine the institution of the presidency. Concerns were also raised by Facebook comments from the President's husband, Prindon Sadriu, who referred to journalists as a “joint criminal enterprise”.

Simultaneously, in February 2022, a competition for a new Director General of the public broadcaster Radio Television of Kosovo (RTK) took place. The previous management had been accused of nepotism, mismanagement, and bias toward political parties. The selection process was suspended after the Balkan Investigative Reporting Network (BIRN) reported irregularities in the evaluation. Some candidates who withdrew at the first stage believe the competition was pre-arranged with a predetermined outcome and that the procedure should be restarted.

According to the EC report on the media environment: “Concerns remain about public smear campaigns, threats, and physical attacks against journalists. The lack of financial independence, exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic, leaves the media vulnerable to political and business interests. The public broadcaster also remains vulnerable to political influence, and a sustainable solution for its funding has yet to be found” (European Commission, b: 5).

Republic of North Macedonia

In its 2021 report, the European Commission noted that “overall, during the reporting period, progress was limited. The general context is favorable to media freedom and allows for critical media reporting, although there was increased tension during the COVID-19 crisis” (European Commission, c: 6).

According to Balkan Insight, in June 2020, the government of the Republic of North Macedonia approved 515,000 Euros to cover the digitalization costs of five national private television stations – Sitel, Kanal 5, Telma, Alsat-M, Alfa TV – and six regional channels. The decision was motivated by the need to support the media during the COVID-19 pandemic but raised questions regarding influence over media independence.

Republic of Serbia

The issue of event coverage in Serbia concerns the claim of national television stations that they are independent and free. When TV management does not explicitly state its biases but operates in alignment with political and/or economic interests, viewers are misled. Therefore, free and independent media are a key factor in the exercise of citizens’ democratic rights and freedoms “by broadening their understanding of the current political and social landscape and encouraging their conscious participation in democratic life” (European Parliament Resolution, 25 November 2020).

Independent Serbian media and investigations still exist, though they are under intense pressure. The case of the regional television station N1 clearly illustrates the state of the media sector. Following investigative reports, the harassment of N1 journalists and its owner has not ceased. Targeted journalists include Jelena Zorić (International Press Institute, 2021), Program Director Jugoslav Ćosić, and reporter Milan Nikić, who was insulted and threatened by members of the ruling Serbian Progressive Party (SNS). Pro-government media conduct campaigns against N1 teams, undermining their authority with slander and insults. Threatening leaflets were even thrown into the station’s yard by unidentified perpetrators. International

NGOs reacted promptly: Reporters Without Borders and the International Press Institute condemned these attempts to intimidate journalists.

In November 2019, Serbian President Aleksandar Vučić was hospitalized due to cardiovascular problems. Pro-government media and officials publicly accused N1 journalist Miodrag Sovilj of causing Vučić's health to deteriorate through his questioning. The questions were related to investigative reports on corrupt practices by ministers of the ruling party's cabinet. Aleksandar Vučić has been its leader since its founding in 2008. After his discharge, Vučić himself refuted speculations linking Miodrag Sovilj's questions to his hospitalization.

Independent media daring to criticize the government in Serbia are also attacked online. According to Reporters Without Borders (RSF, a, 2021), the websites of at least three local Serbian¹³ media outlets were duplicated – including their names and graphic designs (logo, color scheme, site structure). It is assumed that the purpose of these so-called “copycat websites”¹⁴ is to undermine trust in real media and reduce their revenue. Some content is plagiarized, while other publications consist of institutional information about President Vučić and the ruling SNS. At the same time, journalists and editors receive threats (including online), sometimes from representatives of the ruling party. Despite legal action, the prosecution in the Republic of Serbia ruled that the case of duplicated online media did not constitute an intent to mislead the public.

Perhaps the accumulation of events in the Serbian media sphere led to the reaction of Twitter. In August 2021, Twitter applied the label “Serbia state-affiliated media”^{15,16} to the profiles of five national television channels: the public Radio Television of Serbia (RTS) and the private stations Prva, B92, Pink, and Happy. According to the Serbian Center for Contemporary Politics, the Director General of the public media and the owners of the private stations “are considered close to the ruling party, beneficiaries of lucrative business deals with the state, and subject to selective taxation” (Center for Contemporary Politics, 2021: 4).

The OSCE established a Special Election Assessment Mission¹⁷ for the 2020 parliamentary elections in Serbia. It concluded that during the campaign, “the dominance of the ruling party, including in the media, was concerning” (OSCE, 2020:1). It added that “most major television channels and newspapers promote government policy with extensive coverage, limiting the diversity of perspectives” (Ibidem).

Montenegro

The European Commission rated Montenegro's progress in media freedom as “limited”. With the appointment of new management at the public broadcaster Radio and Television of Montenegro (RTCG) in June 2021, the diversity of political content increased. “Overall, the media environment remains highly polarized, often marked by politically biased and unbalanced reporting, including extensive involvement of foreign media from regional

¹³Južne vesti, Ozonpress, and Kolubarske.

¹⁴Duplication of media websites also occurs in Kosovo and North Macedonia.

¹⁵According to Twitter, “State-affiliated media are defined as outlets where the state exercises control over editorial content through financial resources, direct or indirect political pressure, and/or control over production and distribution”. More at: Twitter Help Center, Rules and policies.

¹⁶Accounts of several newspapers were labeled this way: Telegraf, Kurir, Informer, Politika, as well as the Tanjug news agency.

¹⁷Early parliamentary elections were held on April 3, 2022; the OSCE report on the election assessment is forthcoming.

countries, which was particularly noticeable during election campaigns” (European Commission, d: 5).

Serbian influence is increasing in Montenegro’s media sector – three out of four national broadcasters (Nova M, Adria TV, and Vesti TV) are now owned by Serbian media groups Adria Media Group and United Media. It is likely the EC report refers specifically to them. Given the close ties between most Serbian TV stations and Aleksandar Vučić’s ruling SNS, concerns have been raised about attempts to interfere in Montenegro’s internal politics. Meanwhile, the Agency for Electronic Media in Montenegro took a surprising decision: on February 10, 2021, it voted for a three-month ban on retransmitting programs from the Serbian channels Happy and Pink M. According to the regulator, these stations promoted “hatred, intolerance, and discrimination against the Montenegrin ethnicity” (U.S. Department of State, 2020) and were used as a vehicle for an “unprecedented hate speech campaign” (Ibidem) by Serbian media against Montenegro due to the controversial Law on Freedom of Religion¹⁸.

Conclusion

The brief examination of examples from Western Balkan countries over the last three years confirms that what little remains of free and independent journalism is being targeted by state and political leaders. Anti-journalistic rhetoric from politicians and officials is commonplace. A method used to pressure journalists and media owners is the filing of defamation lawsuits. This practice raises a valid question: is it an attempt to protect rights or an attempt to intimidate the media? In the six countries, the protection of the rule of law and fundamental rights is still insufficient to guarantee the functioning of a constitutional state. Efforts to ensure the independence of judicial systems are poorly encouraged and even meet resistance. Regarding compliance with the rule of law in the region, an early 2022 report by the European Court of Auditors acknowledged that “EU actions have had little impact on promoting fundamental rule of law reforms in the Western Balkans. [...] However, due to insufficient political will and a lack of commitment, EU support as a whole has been insufficient to address long-term problems such as judicial dependence, concentration of power, political interference, and corruption” (European Court of Auditors, 2022). In this context, finding justice in a court process is questionable, placing media and journalists facing lawsuits in an extremely disadvantageous position.

Television broadcasters close to the government in the six countries are tolerated and encouraged (e.g., through state projects and advertising). Meanwhile, independent outlets offering critical perspectives on governance face various methods aimed at influencing their editorial policies. The capture of television (and media in general) provides political comfort for the government but undermines their role as a corrective to those in power.

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¹⁸The Law on Freedom of Religion, adopted in December 2019 amid protests in several cities, concerns the property of religious communities and sparked a sharp dispute between Podgorica, Belgrade, and the Serbian Orthodox Church. The law required religious communities to provide documents certifying property ownership from before 1918. The Serbian Orthodox Church claimed it would be deprived of medieval monasteries. This led to a rift between President Milo Đukanović and the Church, whom he accused of pro-Serbian policies.

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